

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN LYMPH NODES UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF MEASLES.

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Abstract: An analysis of the pathomorphological changes developed in the main morphofunctional areas of the lymph nodes of children who died from measles and its complications was carried out, in which morphological data on the pathomorphological changes detected in the lymph nodes in measles and its complicated forms were analyzed. the specificity of changes in the immune system is shown.

Key words: virus, measles, lymph nodes, follicle, paracortical, hyperplasia, morphofunctional, sinuses, capsule, infiltration.

Severity: The causative agent of measles is an RNA virus of the Morbillivirus belonging to the family of paramyxoviruses, which has a spherical shape and a diameter of 120-230 nm. The virus consists of a nucleocapsid - the minus strand of RNA, three proteins and an outer shell formed by matrix proteins and two surface glycoproteins: one of them is hemagglutinin, and the other is a "coupling" protein. Most cases of measles are observed in the winter-spring period (December-May), the incidence increases every 2-4 years [1][2]. The measles virus has a very high negative effect on the immune system, causing the destruction of immune cells: from the first days of the appearance of the rash to the 30th day, a sharp decrease in T-lymphocytes is observed. The measles virus weakens the body's immunity for several years because it causes the death of immune cells that produce antibodies to various infections [3][4][5].

The goals and objectives of the work: to study the specificity of the pathomorphological changes that occur in the general morphological macro and microscopic examinations of the tissues of the lymph nodes of patients who died from measles.

Materials and methods: the medical history and autopsy data of 26 patients who died from measles in the winter and spring of 2024 and were examined at the Fergana Regional Pathology and Anatomy Bureau were analyzed. Autopsy pieces from lymph nodes were fixed in formaldehyde solution (prepared in 10% phosphate buffer) for 72 hours and examined by hematoxylin-eosin staining.

Result: in the study of the autopsy materials of the patients, the capsule of the lymph node is thickened due to the rubella virus, swelling in the subcapsular

zone, fullness in all blood vessels, the germinal centers of the outer cortical lymph nodes are basophilized, the boundaries with the deep cortical layer are unclear, there are also T lymphocytes along with B lymphocytes, and monocytes in all parts. , the presence of inflammatory infiltration consisting of leukocytes, tissue detritus and fibrin threads was determined.

In the next case, in addition to the thickening of the capsule of the lymph node, the increase of large macrophage cells, uneven filling of the blood vessels, the border of the lymph nodes of the outer cortex is unclear, the germinal centers are poorly expressed, and the proliferation of lymphocytes in the trabecular sinuses and the corpuscles of the brain. In some examined micropreparations, the afferent lymphatic channels were destructively changed, infiltrated with leukocytes, swelling in the subcapsular zone, proliferation of large macrophage cells, uneven filling of blood vessels, swelling

Conclusion: due to the influence of the measles virus, the capsule of the lymph nodes is thickened, swollen, lost follicles, diffuse necrosis foci, infiltrated with a large amount of leukocytes, lymphocytes and fibrin in the capsule of the node and between the follicular spaces, and acute lymphadenitis, and in some cases reactive centers of the lymph node. chronic lymphadenitis with hyperplasia, swelling in the capsule and intercellular substance, inflammatory infiltration consisting of many lymphocytes, leukocytes and fibrin in all branches of the lymph node.

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